

Availability and Adequacy of Resources for Business Education Programme Implementation in Public-Owned Colleges of Education in Oyo State

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14885758>

Abstract

This study assessed the availability and adequacy of resources for business education programme implementation in public-owned Colleges of Education in Oyo State. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study, and the population comprised 738 business education students and 36 lecturers, with a sample size of 259 students and 33 lecturers. The research instrument adopted for data collection was a self-developed questionnaire. Frequency count and standard deviation were used to analyze the data collected. The study found that there is a variation in the availability of resources for the implementation of business education programmes in public-owned Colleges of Education in Oyo State, and that most of the resources needed for the successful implementation of business education programmes in the area of study are available but slightly inadequate. The study concluded that the variation observed in the availability and adequacy of both human and material resources for the implementation of business education programme may have serious implications for the quality and efficiency of the programme, if not properly addressed. It was therefore recommended that governments, both federal and state, should ensure the availability and adequacy of resources for the implementation of business education programme through adequate funding and provision of modern equipment and facilities. It was equally recommended that the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) should conduct accreditation exercises in strict adherence to the NCCE Minimum Standards, and any area

of deficiencies should be promptly addressed through appropriate recommendations to the government and its relevant agencies.

Keywords: Assessment, Business Education, Programme Implementation, Colleges of Education

Introduction

Education is the process of acquiring knowledge, skills, attitudes, abilities, competences and the cultural norms of a society by people and to transmit life to the coming generations so as to enhance perpetual development. Therefore, education is a vital instrument for transformation and social change which makes the recipients contribute positively towards the general goal of the nations. There are many disciplines studied by undergraduates in higher educational institutions through which skills can be acquired. Business education is one of them. Business education is a core component of Technical and Vocational Education programmes taught by professionally trained business educators in tertiary institutions for job placement in the society. Business education programme is concerned with teaching the skills, attitudes and knowledge necessary for a successful career in office and business world (Binuomote & Okoli, 2015). Business education is a form of education that enriches basic education for teaching career, entrepreneurship, business understanding, office understanding, office environment and vocational practices (Nwokike, Ezeabii & Jim, 2018). In the view of Onajite (2016), business education encompasses education programme for business, office occupation, economic understanding, entrepreneurship and it seeks to develop in the learners' basic skills for personal use in the future. The primary goal of Business Education is to produce competent, skillful and dynamic business teachers, office administrators and businessmen and woman that will effectively compete in the job market.

In the light of the above, Business Education embraces basic education for teaching career, entrepreneurship, business understanding, office environment and vocational practices. Business education occurs at several levels, such as primary, secondary and tertiary levels. At the tertiary level of education in Nigeria, the philosophy of business education is to make the students understand the concept and philosophy of the national policy on education because of its importance in national development. It was based on this premise that the National Commission for Colleges of Education, NCCE (2020) enumerated the objectives of Business Education as follows, to: produce competent NCE graduates who will teach business subjects in secondary schools and other related educational institutions; produce competent NCE graduates who will epitomize business spirit in the society; produce competent NCE graduates who will commence the development of the much-desired revolution in vocational and entrepreneurial skills from the Primary through Secondary schools; equip graduates with necessary competencies for a post-NCE degree programme in Business Education; and equip graduates with the right business competencies for a life of work in the office as well as for self-employment. Business Education thus expected to produce graduates with the right skills, knowledge, attitude and competencies required for employment either in public or private establishment or become job creators thereby, contributing to national development. With these objectives, the onus is placed on business education to drive economic growth and empowerment as well as generate employment for business education graduates.

However, the actualization of business education programme objectives largely depends on resources availability and adequacy. Meanwhile, the availability and adequacy of resources for

the implementation of business education in Nigeria has been a major concern for stakeholders in the education sector. This assertion is supported by Jim, Nwokike & Ezeabii (2017) who averred that the implementation of business education programme for the attainment of its objectives has always posed a serious concern for business education stakeholders. Considering the high rate of unemployment and poverty in the society, there is a dire need to assess and re-assess business education programme implementation in the public-owned Colleges of Education in Oyo State. This assessment will no doubt be of benefits to stakeholders who are full of concerns towards the implementation of business education programme and provide them with feedbacks on the area of strengths and weaknesses of the implementation of the programme. With these in mind, this study therefore assessed the availability and adequacy of business education programme implementation in public-owned Colleges of Education in Oyo State.

Objectives of the Study

The following were the objectives of this study, to:

1. determine the availability of resources for business education programme implementation in public-owned Colleges of Education in Oyo State;
2. examine the adequacy of available resources for business education programme implementation in public-owned Colleges of Education in Oyo State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. How available are the resources for business education programme implementation in public-owned Colleges of Education in Oyo State?
2. How adequate are the resources for business education programme implementation in public-owned Colleges of Education in Oyo State?

Methodology

A descriptive survey design was adopted for this study, and the population comprised 738 business education students and 36 lecturers in the two public-owned Colleges of Education in Oyo State, namely: Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo and Oyo State College of Education, Lanlate. The sample size used for the study, as determined by Taro Yamane sample size formula, was 259 students and 33 lecturers. Simple random sampling technique was used to select the respondents. The research instrument adopted for the study was a self-developed questionnaire titled: Business Education Programme Assessment Questionnaire (BEPAQ). The instrument was divided into two (2) sections, namely; Sections A and B. Section A focused on demographic characteristics of the respondents while Section B contained items on stakeholders' ratings of the availability and adequacy of resources for the implementation of business education programmes. The research instrument was duly validated by two senior lecturers from the Department of Business Education, one from each of the two Colleges of Education under study. The researchers conducted a pilot study by administering forty (40) copies of the instrument to both Business Education lecturers and students in Osun State College of Education, Ila Orangun, Osun State. The data collected from the pilot study were subjected to Cronbach Alpha reliability test and 0.76 reliability level was obtained, hence the reliability of the instrument was considered reliable for the study. Frequency counts and standard deviation were used to analyze the demographics and answer the research questions respectively. The total population of students and

lecturers as obtained from the Heads of Departments of Business Education in the two Colleges of Education was presented in the table below:

Table 1: Population of Business Education Lecturers and Students in Public-Owned Colleges of Education in Oyo State

S/N	Name of Institution	Lecturers			Students		
		M	F	Total	M	F	Total
1.	Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo.	15	12	27	294	359	653
2.	Oyo State College of Education, Lanlate	04	05	09	33	52	85
	Total	19	17	36	327	411	738

Source: Departmental Records from HODs, 2024

Results

The analysis of the data collected to answer the research questions are presented below:

Table 2: Response Rate Distribution

Response	Valid		Invalid		Total
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	
Students	231	89.2	28	10.8	259
Staff	31	93.9	2	6.1	33
	262	89.7	30	10.3	292

Table 2 displays the distribution of responses obtained from a survey conducted among the respondents i.e., Business Education students and lecturers. The table indicates the frequency and percentage of both valid and invalid responses received from both groups. According to the table, a total of 292 responses were received. Of these responses, 89.2% (231) were valid responses from students, while 10.8% (28) were invalid responses from students. On the other hand, 93.9% (31) of the responses received from lecturers were valid, while 6.1% (2) were invalid. The table indicates an acceptable response rate, with a valid response rate of 89.2% from students and 93.9% from lecturers.

Analysis of Demographic Data

Table 3: School Distribution

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	FCES, Oyo	233	79.8	82.3	79.8
	CoE, Lanlate	59	20.2	17.7	20.2
	Total	292	100.0	100.0	100.0

Table 3 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents from the two public-owned Colleges of Education in Oyo State, Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo and Oyo State College of Education, Lanlate. Out of the 292 respondents, 233 (79.8%) were from FCES, Oyo while 59 (20.2%) were from Lanlate. This indicates that FCES, Oyo has a larger population of students and lecturers who participated in the survey compared to the Oyo State College of Education, Lanlate.

Table 4: Gender Distribution

	Gender	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	117	40.1	40.1	40.1
	Female	175	59.9	59.9	59.9
	Total	292	100.0	100.0	100.0

Table 4 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents by gender. Out of the 292 respondents, 117 (40.1%) were male, while 175 (59.9%) were female.

Analysis of Research Questions

Research Question One: How available are the resources for business education programme implementation in public-owned Colleges of Education in Oyo State?

Table 5 Availability of Business Education Resources

Business Education Resources	Highly Available	Available	Not Available	S.D.	Remarks
Personnel Resources					
Lecturers	-	175 (66.8%)	87 (33.2%)	.6082	Available
Support Staff	-	146 (55.8%)	116 (44.2%)	.7417	Available
Facilities					
Classrooms	14 (5.3%)	160 (61.1%)	88 (33.6%)	.6216	Available
Laboratories/Studios	12 (4.6%)	140 (53.4%)	110 (42.0%)	.7312	Available
Staff Offices	10 (3.8%)	151 (57.7%)	101 (38.5%)	.6320	Available
Departmental Library	-	98 (37.4%)	164 (62.6%)	1.3312	Not Available
Model Office	2 (0.8%)	125 (47.7%)	135 (51.5%)	1.2120	Not available
Internet Facilities	21 (8.0%)	180 (68.7%)	61 (23.3%)	.5654	Available
Equipment and Supplie					
Computers	15 (5.7%)	173 (66.0%)	74 (28.3%)	.6069	Available
Projector	4 (1.5%)	69 (26.3%)	189 (72.2%)	1.5758	Not Available
Electric calculators	8 (3.1%)	59 (22.5%)	195 (74.4%)	1.7735	Not Available
Shredding Machines	27 (10.3%)	192 (73.3%)	43 (16.4%)	0.8341	Available
Filing Equipment	15 (5.7%)	160 (61.1%)	87 (33.2%)	.6311	Available
Duplicating Machine	-	151 (57.6%)	111 (42.4%)	.7440	Available
Perforator	58 (22.1%)	160 (61.1%)	44 (16.8%)	.5232	Available
Scanning Machines	26 (9.9%)	158 (60.3%)	78 (29.8%)	.6309	Available
Cassette Players	61 (23.3%)	168 (64.1%)	33 (12.6%)	.5022	Available

Source: *Field Survey, 2024*

Table 5 presents a survey result on the availability of business education resources in the area of study. The survey collected responses from a lecturers and students, who were asked to indicate whether they considered the resources to be available or not available. The results show that the majority of respondents 66.8% and 55.8% respectively consider lecturers and support staff to be available for the implementation of business education programmes. In terms of material resources, the availability of different facilities and equipment varied considerably. Classroom, laboratory/studio, staff offices and internet facilities were considered to be available with a percentage ranging from 53.4% to 68.7%. Whereas, departmental library and model office were

considered unavailable. On equipment and supply, shredding machines, scanning machine, cassette players, and perforators were considered to be available by the majority of respondents (ranging from 60.3% to 73.3%). The availability of duplicating machine and filing equipment received more mixed responses, with 57.6% and 61.1% of respondents considering them to be available, respectively. On the other hand, projector and electric calculators were considered to be unavailable by the respondents.

Research Question Two: How adequate are the resources for business education programme implementation in public-owned Colleges of Education in Oyo State?

Table 6: Adequacy of Business Education Resources

Business Education Resources	Highly Adequate	Adequate	Not Adequate	S.D.	Remarks
Personnel Resources					
Lecturers	12 (4.6%)	130 (49.6%)	120 (45.8%)	.7713	Adequate
Support Staff	-	70 (26.7%)	192 (73.3%)	1.5695	Not Adequate
Facilities					
Classrooms	-	92 (35.1%)	170 (64.9%)	1.7701	Not Adequate
Laboratories/Studios	2 (0.8%)	104 (39.7%)	156 (59.5%)	1.5221	Not Adequate
Staff Offices	-	102 (38.9%)	160 (61.1%)	1.6011	Not Adequate
Departmental Library	3 (1.1%)	94 (35.9%)	165 (63.0%)	1.6324	Not Adequate
Model Office	5 (1.9%)	83 (31.7%)	174 (66.4%)	1.7205	Not Adequate
Internet Facilities	33 (12.6%)	38 (52.7%)	91 (34.7%)	.8013	Adequate
Equipment and Supplies					
Computers	11 (4.2%)	108 (41.2%)	143 (54.6%)	1.4023	Not Adequate
Projector	5 (1.9%)	84 (32.1%)	173 (66.0%)	1.7205	Not Adequate
Electric calculators	-	91 (34.7%)	171 (65.3%)	1.7053	Not Adequate
Shredding Machines	19 (7.3%)	167 (63.7%)	76 (29.0%)	.7108	Adequate
Filing Equipment	23 (8.8%)	158 (60.3%)	81 (30.9%)	.6300	Adequate
Duplicating Machine	6 (2.3%)	91 (34.7%)	165 (63.0%)	1.6951	Not Adequate
Perforator	31 (11.8%)	143 (54.6%)	88 (33.6%)	.6996	Adequate
Scanning Machines	31 (11.8%)	164 (62.6%)	67 (25.6%)	.5005	Adequate
Cassette Players	36 (13.8%)	151 (57.6%)	75 (28.6%)	.5231	Adequate

Source: *Field Survey, 2024*

Table 6 presents the responses of participants on the adequacy of business education resources to the implementation of the programme. The slight majority of the respondents (54.2%) indicated that the number of lecturers available for the implementation of business education programme is adequate. Also, a whopping majority of the respondents (73.3%) were of the view that the number of supporting staff available is grossly inadequate. However, there were variations in the perceived adequacy of material (facilities and equipment) resources. While it was indicated that internet facilities, shredding machine, filing equipment, perforator, scanning machine and cassette were adequate, other facilities and equipment such as classrooms, laboratories,

departmental library, model office, staff offices, computers, duplicating machine, projector and others supplies are not adequate.

Discussion of Findings

The results of the survey indicate that there is a variation in the availability of resources for the implementation of business education programmes in public-owned Colleges of Education in Oyo State. The availability of lecturers and support staff is considered to be high by the majority of respondents, which shows the primacy of human capital in any educational programme. According to Mukuka, & Akakandelwa (2016), the quality of teaching and learning in business education is largely determined by the availability and efficiency of lecturers and support staff. On the other hand, the availability of material resources varies considerably, with some facilities and equipment being more available than others. This finding is consistent with the observation by Oikonomou, Hadjidakou, & Serafeimidis (2020) that the availability of resources and facilities is an important determinant of the successful implementation of business education programmes. The variation in the availability of material resources may have implications for the quality and efficiency of business education programmes implementation. For instance, the unavailability of departmental library and model office will shortchange the students from in accessing subject-specific learning materials, and hinder them from having a firsthand experience of a workable office setting. Also, the limited availability of projector and electric calculator may constrain the ability of lecturers to use multimedia resources in teaching and learning, thereby hindering the delivery of efficient presentations, which are important in enhancing the understanding and retention of knowledge among students.

The findings of the study further reveal that most of the resources needed for the successful implementation of business education programmes in the public-owned colleges of education in Oyo State are available but slightly inadequate. The number of lecturers available were rated as slightly adequate for the implementation of the programme, while support staff received a lower rating of adequacy. Majority of the facilities, equipment and supplies; such as, classrooms, studios, staff offices, model offices, departmental library, computers, projectors, duplicating machines and among others were considered inadequate for the implementation of business education programme in the study area. These findings are consistent with Adeyemo & Adeyinka (2017), and Olumide & Ademola (2019) who identified that inadequate provision of facilities and shortage of personnel top the list of challenges in implementing business education programme. In like manner, Onyesom & Okolocha (2013), and Umoru & Oluwalola (2016) submitted that there are inadequate teachers and other technical staff as well as equipment and supplies in relation to the NCCE minimum standards in business education programmes of Nigerian tertiary institutions. Okoro (2017) equally reported that business education as a course needs a blend of human and non-human resources, in the right proportion, for the successful implementation of the programme.

Conclusion

This study concludes that the variation observed in the availability and adequacy of both human and material resources for the implementation of business education programme in the public-owned Colleges of Education in Oyo State may have serious implications for the quality and efficiency of the programme, if not properly addressed. Policymakers and stakeholders need to address the gaps identified in the study to improve the implementation of the programme.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made, that;

1. Governments, both federal and state, should ensure availability and adequacy of resources for the implementation of business education programme in the public-owned Colleges of Education in Oyo State. This can be achieved through proper funding, adequate staffing, and provision of modern equipment and facilities.
2. The National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) should conduct accreditation exercises in strict adherence to the NCCE Minimum Standards, and any area of deficiencies should be promptly addressed through appropriate recommendations to the government and its relevant agencies.
3. The management of the institutions should further collaborate with industry players, non-government organizations, philanthropists and alumni associations to ensure the availability and adequacy of resources needed for the successful implementation of business education programme.

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